

RF Shield design for transmit coils to reduce acoustic noise in MRI

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Synopsis

Motivation: Eddy currents induced in the RF shield cause vibrations which translate into acoustic noise.

Goals: To develop an RF shield that minimises eddy currents and preserve the B_1^+ efficiency.

Approach: It was established that eddy-currents induced in the RF shield of the transmit coil are the primary source of acoustic noise. The conventional slotted double layered RF shield thus was replaced by a segmented phosphor bronze mesh to minimise eddy currents and acoustic noise.

Results: Measurements performed at both ear locations of an anthropometric phantom demonstrate that the segmented PBM-based RF shield reduces the acoustic noise by up to 10dB.

Impact: Acoustic noise reduction could be achieved by using segmented PBM without compromising the transmit B_1 field compared to the conventional double-layered slotted shield. Further improvements could be achieved by different mesh configurations besides the one implemented in this work.

Introduction:

The 7T scanner at the University of California, Berkeley, is the first of the NexGen 7T scanners equipped with the investigational Impulse head gradient coil (Siemens Healthineers, Erlangen Germany) capable of achieving a maximum gradient strength of 200 mT/m and slew rate of 900 T/m/s per axis¹. The changing magnetic flux from the time varying gradient magnetic field induces eddy currents on any conductive surface. This translates into resistive heat and vibrations and unwanted acoustic noise, which can be highly uncomfortable for the subject.

Most transmit arrays used for brain imaging at 7T are locally shielded to minimise radiation loss and improve robustness of coil tuning inside the scanner bore. The RF shield is typically realised using a flexible double-layered PCB. Each layer is slotted to reduce eddy currents and the copper strips on the two layers are offset to form a high value capacitor, thereby the shield is continuous for RF. Heavily slotting the RF shield by minimising the strip width can minimise eddy currents but can also reduce shielding efficiency and thus be detrimental to the transmit B_1 efficiency. Phosphor Bronze Mesh (PBM) has been used in the past to reduce gradient-induced eddy currents and has demonstrated effective RF shielding to protect electronics equipment in MRI². In this work, a new type of RF shield based on PBM has been developed to substantially reduce the acoustic noise while simultaneously improving the transmit efficiency.

Methods:

The study was performed on an 8-channel transmit 64-channel receive head coil³. The reference RF shield is a conventional two layered design consisting of 34 longitudinal strips in each layer with a strip width is 32mm and copper thickness of 18um (figure 1A). Although perhaps not obvious at first sight, it was established through a series of experiments (presented separately in this meeting) that the

primary source of acoustic noise beyond a cut-off frequency in the kHz range was in our setup the eddy currents induced in the RF shield, and not the vibrations of the gradient coil. The PBM shield consisted of 380 mesh count per inch (Shandong Xingying Technology, China) and segmented into 16 longitudinal strips with a 2mm gap. The adjacent strips were bridged together with 1000pF capacitors to make the shield continuous for RF (figure 1B).

Sound pressure levels were measured using a dedicated sensor connected to a frontend and software (Bruël & Kjaer, Naerum, Denmark). To get a transfer function versus frequency, measurements were first performed with constant amplitude ($G=2$ mT/m) and linear frequency sweeps between 0 and 3.2 kHz in 2 min, for each gradient axis individually. Second, because the spectrum of MR sequences can be widespread, sound levels were also measured with EPI sequences at different echo spacings (0.56, 0.61, 0.66, 0.71, 0.76, 0.81, 0.96 and 1.01 ms) at constant gradient amplitude (76 mT/m), bandwidth and with the 3 readout axes (X, Y, Z) separately. The measurements were repeated at both ear locations of an anthropomorphic phantom (figure 2). To verify the change of the shield was not detrimental to the transmit efficiency, an Actual Flip angle Imaging (AFI) sequence was implemented to measure the B_1^+ field in CP mode.

Results:

The B_1 maps measured by driving the coil in CP mode, using the same reference voltage, are shown in figure 3. The wider strips of the PBM shield improved the overall transmit efficiency, yielding a gain in the center of about 15%.

Figure 4 shows the acoustic transfer functions where a significant reduction of acoustic noise at high frequencies with the PBM shield can be observed, consistently with eddy-currents being the primary cause of acoustic noise. Although the gain versus frequency is not systematic, the general trend is a drop of acoustic energy above 1.5 kHz, with some peaks even reduced sometimes by 10 dB. Figure 5 shows the sound pressure values acquired with EPI. Besides $ES=0.61$ ms where the PBM shield made it worse by 2dB at the right ear and with the Y axis, the gains are systematic and vary between 0 and 9 dB. These results establish that current loops are disturbed and limited by segmenting and meshing the conductive surfaces, consequently minimising acoustic noise.

Discussion and conclusion:

We have demonstrated that acoustic noise reduction could be achieved through different RF shield properties, without compromising the transmit B_1 field. Now that eddy-currents in the RF shield have been identified as the main cause, at least in our setup, this work paves the way for more improvements. We envisage creating smaller segments along the axial and longitudinal directions and overlapping the adjacent segments could further reduce the eddy currents and will be the subject of future work.

References:

1. D Feinberg Et al., ISMRM 2021
2. Lee BJ et al., MRM 79 (2018)
3. Shajan G et al., ISMRM 2022

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Figure 1: (A) Photograph of the reference double layered RF shield realised using flexible PCB. There are a total of 34 longitudinal strips of width 32 mm each. (B) Photograph of the PBM shield with 16 strips. The adjacent strips are bridged with 1000pF capacitors.

Figure 2: Sound pressure level sensor was attached near the left and right ear of a head shaped phantom filled with tissue equivalent solution.

Figure 3: B1 maps acquired in CP mode demonstrate improved transmit performance with the PBM shield. The mesh structure allows wider strips to be used without increasing eddy currents. There is a rough gain of 15% in B_1^+ between the two configurations.

Figure 4: Acoustic transfer function (in linear scale) demonstrating substantial noise reduction for all three gradient axes while using the phosphor bronze mesh. Up to 10dB reduction could be observed. Measurements were performed on each axis separately at constant gradient amplitude of 2 mT/m.

Figure 5: Comparison of acoustic noise level in EPI at different echo spacings. Here again, the PBM shield demonstrated almost systematically lower noise levels. The axis indicates the readout direction of the EPI sequence.